

IMPORTANCE OF THE QUALITY OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION FOR EUROPEANIZATION

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Public administration plays a prominent role in state transition and modernization processes. Therefore, the quality of public administration affects transition processes in Eastern European states on their way to joining the European Union. This hypothesis is proven by analysing former socialist or communist countries that became members of the European Union during the two major waves of accession in 2004 and 2007 because, to do so, they had to implement internal modernization processes to more democracy and a market economy. A quantitative research design is used to investigate whether a functioning administration has a strong positive impact on transition, its effectiveness and sustainability. The result shows that a well-functioning administration significantly promotes transition processes and has a positive impact on transition to more democracy and a market economy.

Key words: Public Administration; democracy; market economy; European Union; Europeanization.

1 CONTEXT

The object of the study is to determine whether the quality of public administration affects the transformation of East European states on their way into the European Union (EU). The EU accession process promotes such transformation since a state that wishes to join the EU needs to implement standards that support democracy and a market economy, and this encompasses the transition from a planned to a market economy and, accordingly, from an autocratic to a democratic form of government.

Starting from the 1990s, many Eastern European states faced dramatic changes. Following the fall of the Eastern Bloc, they turned to the West, more prosperity and democratic forms of government. At the end of the 1980s, no-one would have believed that centrally planned economies would be integrated in the EU. Besides

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having to overcome ideological differences, the largely successful transition to market-economic democracies is remarkable because there was no plan for outside support such as, for example, that given to the German Democratic Republic by the Federal Republic of Germany. Then, the EU granted accession to twelve new countries within a relatively short period of time from 2004 to 2007, among them ten former socialist or communist states. The latter, also called transition countries, are the research units of this study: Bulgaria, Estonia, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, the Czech Republic and Hungary. These post-socialist countries underwent consolidation. Dictatorships became democratic states, whose elites relied on a market economy as the foundation for facing the challenges of a competitive model of democracy. In just a short time, the ten countries diametrically changed their form of government and, in this respect, were able to comply with the standards required by the EU. Although Cyprus and Malta also joined the EU in 2004, they are not considered transition countries and, thus, are excluded from the analysis for lack of comparability. Furthermore, Croatia joined much later (2013). The country was not part of the enlargement between 2004 and 2007 and, hence, it is not included in the study (Willershausen 2002; Berend 2005, 401–416; Blokker 2005, 503; Haensch and Holtmann 2008, 610; Ismayr 2010, 9).

2 CURRENT STATE OF RESEARCH AND THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

The national governments, public administrations or political institutions of the countries under review have been the subject of numerous studies. So, for example, Rice (1992), Balázs (1993), Newland (1996), Ellison (2007) or Kukovič (2013) studied the situation of political institutions in post-Communist countries in Central and Eastern Europe. How the EU exerts pressure to initiate reforms in potential members also has been the topic of numerous research articles. Accordingly, for example, Hughes, Sasse and Gordon (2004), Papadimitriou and Phinnemore (2004), Pippan (2004), Schimmelfennig and Sedelmeier (2004), Sedelmeier (2008), Epstein and Sedelmeier (2008) as well as Toplak (2011) have considered this subject. Questions regarding transformation were analysed, amongst others, e.g. by Weidenfeld (2001) (see all in all Busch and Matthes 2004; Reiners 2013a; Busch et al. 2014; Böttger 2020; Lippert 2020; Libman and Platzer 2021; Reiners 2023; Beichelt 2022; de Munter 2023 or country-specific e.g. Ahrens and Zweynert 2012; Kasekamp and Treichel 2013; Cianciara 2019; Damian 2019; Deimel 2020; Sapper, Weichsel and Handl 2023).

In addition to the fundamental findings of EU research, another aspect worth looking at is how the processes can be comprehended theoretically. By expressing their intention to join the EU, the countries gave the EU power to induce change in institutions and policies. Based on the assumption that the public administration is the central actor in this respect, it is reasonable to assume that measures will be implemented much more effectively when it performs efficiently. This is illustrated by the variables as well as index values and rankings in Section 4. Therefore, implementing the necessary reform steps in the process and overcoming behavioural patterns calls for appropriate political steering by the governments and the respective public administrations because they explicitly have operative responsibility (Schimmelfennig and Sedelmeier 2004, 126–141; Schimmelfennig and Sedelmeier 2007, 675–677).

High-quality public administrations can efficiently implement policies and generally execute the political demands of the government effectively. Qualitative public administration is characterized by professional staff, clear-cut

decision-making rules and structures, objectivity, transparency and responsibility. Such administration acts as an intermediary, interwoven with the government in the overall machinery of government. It is, so to say, the "transmission belt," between the state and its citizens; and this alone signals its central status (see Rice 1992; Balázs 1993, 75–88; Ellison 2007; Haensch and Holtmann 2008, 620–625).

Political programs and legislative procedures usually are initiated there. Even if the initiatives originate with other actors, the proposals, more often than not, are handled by administrative staff in the government departments or ministries. Accordingly, public administration is at the foreground of implementing EU standards and specific transformation measures since, in most cases, it is the first instance to be notified of the necessary changes required by EU bodies. It sets standards, works out the details of laws and, ultimately, is responsible for their realization and implementation. When the public administration does not operate efficiently, the result could well be stagnation of the transition process (see Scharpf 2000, 323; Haensch and Holtmann 2008, 606–630; Nicolaidis 2004). Therefore, all in all, it is plausible that the quality of public administration significantly affects the process because when public administration is addressed as an actor, its central role in the political cycle inevitably becomes evident, for example, in connection with setting the agenda, formulating policy or implementing policy (see only Schuppert 2000 or Seibel 2016).

Almost necessarily, this view directs attention to the ensuing question whether reforms depend on the structure of political institutions or structures have an impact on the transition process and its results. The clear-cut answer of political science, neo-institutionalism or, for example, actor-centred institutionalism is: "Institutions matter." In fact, a core neo-institutional assumption is that institutions have significant influence on political events and that, to a large extent, results can be traced back to institutional origins; and so, particularly the public administration plays a prominent role in this context (see i.e. Hall and Taylor 1996; Scharpf 2000; Ostrom 2008; Reiners 2008, 30–31, 89; Peters 2019, 281–285).

In many cases, it is evident that, in addition to the quality of the public administration, precarious financial framework conditions promote a paradigm shift. Therefore, in view of the control variable, the focus is on whether modernization is induced by financial difficulties. The situation of the public budget can be determined by specific key indicators. Such figures as the increase in debt, overall public debt or public debt per capita, which is even more appropriate because it is related to the population, are suitable for this purpose (see e.g. Reiners 2008, 39). Therefore, the latter debt level allows an even more precise assessment of the economic situation of the respective countries than the other factors. In many instances, the economic starting position or considerable external pressure stimulates such processes because political, social and/or economic crises or preliminary stages of such crises and the pressure created by them are frequently considered a trigger for state transformation as manifested, for example, by learning theories. Economic pressure in particular frequently is the motivation and drive to undertake modernization measures. In this connection, it becomes evident that whenever features of crises are perceived strongly, the willingness to intervene in institutionalized structures and traditions rises, even if financial restrictions may limit the scope of modernization (see only Hall 1993; Rose 1993, 2004; Sabatier and Jenkins-Smith 1993; Biegelbauer 2013; Haensch and Holtmann 2008, 607; Reiners 2016, 17–18).

3 HYPOTHESIS AND THE EU'S PROFILE OF REQUIREMENTS

The study concentrates on common lines of development and differences between various public administrations. All research units exhibit fundamentally similar systemic preconditions for transformation, because they all originated in socialist or communist systems and, moreover, had to meet the same EU accession standards within a tight time frame. For all these countries, the process resulted in their request being fulfilled, albeit this cannot be taken for granted: Before a country is allowed to join the EU, standards and directives need to be fulfilled and implemented. When accession is granted, it indicates that the public administration of the country concerned functions properly. Therefore, it can be assumed that high-quality administrations are better able to implement changes to democracy and a market economy effectively and sustainably. Presumably, they play a very important role as regards the implementation of EU standards and modernization processes. The normative characteristics or qualifications of "high-quality" administrations can be expressed empirically based on index values and rankings in the set of variables that will be presented later. The assumptions and theoretical foundations lead to the nomological hypothesis (Schimmelfennig and Sedelmeier 2004, 675–677; Ellison 2007, 221–232; Haensch and Holtmann 2008, 606–630; see e.g. Mayer and Palmowski 2004, 579–582):

The higher the quality of the public administration, the better the course of the EU transition process.

It is hard to find arguments against the thesis because – not least due to the theoretical context – it is intuitively plausible that the quality of the public administration has a considerable impact on the transformation process. In fact, it suggests itself that the hypothesis may be logically consistent simply based on the theoretical explanations.

The EU sets requirements for candidate countries because only countries that demonstrate progress in establishing democracy and a market economy have a chance of achieving EU candidacy (Schimmelfennig 2007, 126–141). The EU requires that liberal-democratic standards be implemented for gaining accession to the community. By making the implementation of policy reforms a prerequisite for accession, the EU can influence the transformation process. Schimmelfennig and Sedelmeier find that the EU imposed high requirements on Central and East European countries, on those that were part of the two large waves of accession, and thereby exerted pressure on the countries (2004, 669).

Formally, several steps need to be completed before a country can become a member of the EU. The Copenhagen Criteria that were set up in 1993 stipulate that candidates need to demonstrate a functioning market economy and the ability to assume the obligations and goals connected to EU membership. In addition, political criteria need to be fulfilled: democracy, rule of law, human rights and respect for minorities. Signing the Europe Agreement then marks the preliminary stage of official accession negotiations. It needs to be ratified by all EU members and the state concerned. It comprises initial contractual agreements to ensure economic and political alignment with the community. The research units of this study still signed the Europe Agreement with the EU; it was later replaced by the Stabilization and Association Agreement. This step per se sets high demands on the public administrations: they need to expend enormous resources and work efficiently without having any assurance of gaining membership (Haensch and Holtmann 2008, 610–611). Once the accession

negotiations have been successful, the next step is attaining the official status of an accession candidate, which is followed by accession as a full member and, finally, the ratification of the accession treaty. Apart from Bulgaria and Romania, eight countries opted to let their citizens decide about EU accession by direct vote in a referendum (Gabriel 2008, 190–193; Trüdinger 2008, 221–223; Haensch and Holtmann 2008, 610–612).

4 METHOD AND RESEARCH DESIGN

No comparison can reproduce reality in all its complexity. Comparisons not only involve many variables but also a limited number of suitable cases, which, ultimately, leads to many degrees of freedom for explaining the variance. Therefore, the focus is on the probable determining factors and the probable central actor. The analytic focus is on states that had basically similar preconditions and gained accession to the EU within a limited period during the large enlargement in the mid-2000s (see e.g. Hartmann 1995, 32; Reiners 2008, 80–82).

The correlation of the variables is checked by means of a quantitative paradigm. The comparative approach follows the most-different ("method of difference") or most-similar systems design with a view to the variances in the dependent variable or rather the transformation. It needs to be determined to what extent the quality of the public administration can be used to predict the course of the transformation (Mill 1846; Hartmann 1995, 30; see Lijphardt 1975, 164; Ragin 1987, 37; Kühnel and Krebs 2006; see critical: Przeworski and Teune 1982, 34–36; Dogan and Pelassy 1984, 117–119). Observations for nine points in time are available for each country. In the end, ten units with 90 observations are studied. The evaluations basically concentrate on the period starting with EU accession and the subsequent sixteen years. In view of the data available for the dependent variable, it would not be possible to study a more retrograde period. For this reason, the period under review begins in 2004 and is oriented to the future – almost to the present – because, it goes without saying, that transformation has not been completed at the time of accession, even though certain criteria need to be fulfilled to gain accession. All in all, the manner of proceeding provides an overview of the differences between the states and developments.

Numeric values for the independent variable, i.e. the quality of public administration, are obtained by using the data of the Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI) of the World Bank for nine points in time in cycles of two years from 2004 to 2020. These cycles were chosen because data on the dependent variable are only available at intervals of two years. The first point in time (2004) reflects the EU accession of eight states; Bulgaria and Romania joined the EU later (2007). The pressure to carry out economic modernization, measured by the level of public debt in relation to the population, is taken as another independent variable or rather control variable for the same points in time to prove that the first variable mentioned may possibly have a relatively high explanatory power. Data from the transformation index of the Bertelsmann Stiftung (BTI) are used to determine the dependent variable, the transformation, in two-year intervals for the period from 2006 to 2022. By reason of a certain time lag, the data of the independent variable are correlated to those of the dependent variable but staggered by a time lag of two years because it is obvious that the processes will run into some delays and the causes will not have an immediate effect.

4.1 Independent variables: Quality of the public administration and public debt

The quality of the public administration is operationalized using the Worldwide Governance Indicators. The six indicators compiled by the World Bank for almost all countries and regions permit a realistic assessment of a state's governance and steering capability and help to describe a state's general situation. The indicators are generated from statistics, evaluations of experts and surveys that are provided by research institutes, think tanks, NGOs and international organizations. The indicators are as follows: voice and accountability, political stability and absence of violence, government effectiveness, regulatory quality, rule of law, and control of corruption (World Bank 2022a).

Only one indicator is used in the study because it, to put it precisely, is basically concerned solely with operationalizing the quality of the public administration system. The government effectiveness indicator (GE) or, in other words, the performance of the government and, thus, the public administration associated with it, provides detailed information on the quality of the administration, its independence of political pressure and the quality of policy implementation. Since the GE indicator is based on several representative and non-representative sources, it gives a comprehensive assessment of the public administration. This, in turn, ensures that the analysis is largely well-founded. The measuring unit of the indicator is the percentile rank of the country in relation to all other countries. The higher the value, the better the performance of the public administration. Table 1 shows that there are variances: Such countries as Estonia, Slovenia or the Czech Republic have higher values, whereas Bulgaria and Romania lag behind. The ten units have the following index values and rankings:

TABLE 1: INDEPENDENT VARIABLE, QUALITY OF PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION WGI - GE

	2004	2006	2008	2010	2012	2014	2016	2018	2020	Median	Rank
BG	58.71	51.71	50.97	54.55	55.45	49.04	56.19	57.14	43.81	53.06	9
EE	80.10	83.90	84.47	82.30	77.25	80.29	81.90	83.33	87.62	82.35	1
CZ	79.10	83.41	79.13	77.03	76.30	81.25	78.57	78.57	78.57	79.11	3
HU	77.11	77.56	73.30	71.77	69.67	72.12	68.57	68.10	70.00	72.02	7
LV	71.64	72.20	69.42	72.73	74.88	77.88	78.10	79.52	76.19	74.73	5
LT	75.12	73.66	70.39	73.68	74.41	78.85	80.48	80.48	81.43	76.50	4
PL	67.16	64.39	67.48	70.81	70.62	74.52	72.38	71.90	64.29	69.28	8
RO	51.24	49.76	43.69	51.20	49.29	62.02	49.52	46.67	41.43	49.42	10
SK	78.11	76.59	77.18	75.12	73.93	75.00	74.76	72.38	69.05	74.68	6
SI	79.60	80.00	83.01	80.86	80.57	79.81	82.86	82.38	84.76	81.54	2

Source: World Bank 2022b (values rounded); BG: Bulgaria, EE: Estonia, CZ: Czech Republic, HU: Hungary, LV: Latvia, LT: Lithuania, PL: Poland, RO: Romania, SK: Slovakia, SI: Slovenia (Österreichische Nationalbank 2024).

Economic modernization pressure, measured by public debt in relation to the population, seconds as independent (control) variable. Based on, amongst other things, fundamental learning theories, it can be deduced that economic preconditions frequently are important for state transformation, particularly with respect to stimulating transition (Reiners 2016, 17–18). In view of the theoretical context, the control variable suggests itself, even if only to prove that the quality of public administration is very important. The data are as follows:

TABLE 2: INDEPENDENT CONTROL VARIABLE – DEBT PER CAPITA IN EURO

	2004	2006	2008	2010	2012	2014	2016	2018	2020	Median
BG	822	778	631	862	1,026	1,509	2,212	1,953	2,531	1,369
EE	295	371	380	556	1,037	1,220	1,493	1,363	3,355	1,119
CZ	2,154	2,668	2,964	4,210	5,315	4,717	5,546	5,384	6,637	4,399
HU	3,873	4,670	5,188	5,981	6,088	6,085	7,787	7,927	9,557	6,351
LV	567	562	1,228	2,604	3,075	3,431	4,510	4,752	5,838	2,952
LT	809	1,011	1,007	2,470	3,456	3,800	4,887	4,631	7,239	3,257
PL	1,948	2,709	3,024	3,876	4,347	4,155	5,506	5,414	6,932	4,212
RO	428	454	595	1,354	1,823	2,231	2,909	3,087	4,686	1,952
SK	2,882	2,626	2,479	3,892	5,462	5,654	7,067	6,903	8,828	5,088
SI	2,996	3,252	2,779	5,124	7,347	11,032	13,893	13,165	15,592	8,353

Source: Länderdaten 2022 (values rounded).

4.2 Dependent variable: Transformation

The dependent variable is operationalized using the Bertelsmann Transformation Index (BTI/Bertelsmann Stiftung 2022). The Bertelsmann Stiftung provides two indices: the Status Index indicates the status of transformation, and the Governance Index assesses the quality of political steering with respect to the transformation (for this reason, it will be referred to as Management Index). The Status Index shows how far the transition to democracy and a market economy has progressed. In contrast to narrow definitions of democracy, the BTI's understanding of democracy is broader and includes additional criteria. Thus, although objections may be raised, democracy is interconnected with a market economy both empirically and functionally because democratic and economic developments are not always necessarily linked to one another, as demonstrated by China.

For every two-year evaluation period, the Bertelsmann Stiftung analyses and evaluates the situation in more than 100 countries to draw up the indices. This study uses the Status Index because, contrary to the Management Index, it provides information on the progress of transformation without including other factors. Thus, by using the Status Index, the dependent variable can be operationalized in such a way that it only assesses the transformation proper. Five political and seven economic criteria as well as 32 sub-categories are assessed by qualified country experts. The research units are all sovereign states that cannot yet be considered a consolidated democracy with a social market economy.

The Status Index calculates the average of the scores given for the dimensions of "political transition" and "economic transition." Political transition is formed by the average rating of five political criteria (statehood, political participation, rule of law, stability of democratic institutions, political and social integration) with altogether 18 sub-categories, and economic transition is formed by the average of seven economic criteria (socioeconomic level of development, organization of market and competition, monetary and fiscal stability, private property, social organization, economic performance, sustainability) with altogether 14 sub-categories.

Only the BTI's Status Index is used to minimize the risk of assessing a tautology because the independent and dependent variables used in the indices sometimes have similar indicators; moreover, it is adjusted for both criteria. Thus, the following categories of BTI are eliminated as regards the quality of administration (GE): Basic administration structures, effective power to govern, stability of democratic institutions and market organization. With respect to the state of public debt in a country, the following BTI categories are excluded: Socio-economic barriers and performance. Other categories which may be considered concordant in the broadest sense are retained. In fact, it was determined in this

context that other adjustments do not yield additional significant deviations. The two BTIs (unadjusted and adjusted) correlate highly with one another (an R^2 value of 0.98). Ultimately, it is insignificant which BTI is used. The table below shows the values of the adjusted Status Index as well as the resulting index values and rankings. The maximum number of points is 10.0, which indicates an optimal transformation:

TABLE 3: DEPENDENT VARIABLE, STATUS OF TRANSFORMATION BTI – STATUS-INDEX ADJUSTED

	2006	2008	2010	2012	2014	2016	2018	2020	2022	Median	Rank
BG	8.18	8.55	8.44	8.43	8.31	8.19	8.06	8.00	7.76	8.21	8
EE	9.30	9.39	9.37	9.39	9.49	9.59	9.62	9.66	9.55	9.48	2
CZ	9.32	9.48	9.63	9.58	9.55	9.46	9.60	9.57	9.39	9.51	1
HU	9.24	9.32	9.24	8.58	8.18	7.65	7.34	7.00	6.73	8.14	9
LV	8.28	8.63	8.55	8.45	8.52	8.68	8.76	8.83	8.90	8.62	7
LT	9.06	9.24	9.12	9.10	9.03	9.26	9.40	9.38	9.33	9.21	4
PL	8.99	8.72	9.00	9.08	9.24	9.28	8.74	8.32	8.05	8.82	6
RO	8.04	8.34	8.33	8.34	8.10	8.18	8.26	7.72	7.89	8.13	10
SK	9.01	9.18	9.21	8.90	8.79	8.80	8.66	8.74	8.91	8.91	5
SI	9.52	9.49	9.52	9.44	9.15	9.01	9.07	9.09	8.82	9.24	3

Source: Bertelsmann Stiftung 2022 (values rounded).

The interval-scaled rankings shown in Tables 1 and 3 provide an expanded overview and prove helpful for interpreting the result. If the rankings of GE and the adjusted BTI are compared by means of the average values, it already becomes evident that the individual rankings remain mostly unchanged. This supports the assumption that the hypothesis may point in the postulated direction. Then the multiple linear regression is calculated using the index values. The following regression result shows how the independent variables or the two predictors correlate with the values of the dependent values.

5 RESULTS

The results are based on the index values. First, the values from the regression analysis are depicted in a coordinate system and, for reasons of clarity, only with regard to the dominant independent variable (GE), correlated with the adjusted BTI, because the independent control variable seems to be rather marginal and, in particular, proves that GE has a relatively high explanatory power:

FIGURE 1: RESULT OF THE REGRESSION ANALYSIS

Source: Author's own illustration.

The values of the independent variable are plotted on the x axis and those of the dependent variable are plotted on the y axis. The positive relation between quality of the public administration and transition is evident. As shown below, a country's state of public debt plays a marginal role with respect to transformation. Ultimately, this supports the explanatory force of quality of public administration as the decisive value. The regression line for quality of public administration explains the different values relatively well. The value described provides information about the strength of the linear correlation. All in all, this shows a mediocre relationship. The regression provides the following information in detail, shown with adjusted BTI:

TABLE 4: REGRESSION STATISTICS

	GE and debts adjusted with BTI
Multiple correlation coefficient	0.7614
Coefficient of determination R²	0.5797
Standard error	0.4129
Research observations	90
Coefficient GE	0.0445
Coefficient debts	-6.9107E-05
Test size F	60.0055
Critical F-value	4.2013E-17
p-value GE	6.0534E-18
p-value debts	1.6314E-05
Significance level	0.05
Coefficient of determination R² GE	0.4791
Coefficient of determination R² debts	0.0059

Source: Author's own illustration (values rounded to four decimal places).

Ninety observations for ten research units at nine points in time were available for the regression analysis. The coefficient of determination (R^2) is fundamental for the interpretation. It is insignificant and non-correlated for public debt (an R^2 value of 0.0059). This is different regarding the quality of public administration. The correlation of GE indicates an R^2 value of 0.48; moreover, both independent variables together indicate an R^2 value of 0.58. The explained percentage of the variance in the dependent variable is 0.61 for the non-adjusted BTI. Therefore, this value and the quality of the regression model are in a medium range, which means that the statistical model explains a larger percentage of the variance in the dependent variable. Accordingly, the model explains 61% and, following adjustment, 58% of the variation of the index values of BTI. The differences after adjustment, with minimally different values, can be neglected. The adjustment shows that no significant changes are involved and, contrary to the assumption stated above, the risk of a tautology does not emerge.

The study dispensed with other regression models because of the relatively small population and the limited amount of data, which, vice versa, justifies the method that was chosen. Since the study works with a relatively low number of cases, it seems appropriate to look at possible outliers to determine whether they may affect the overall result and to consider the robustness of the results as well. It should be noted that the status of democracy may well have changed for the

worse in some countries. In addition, the regression data showed that, in terms of figures, only Hungary stands out as an outlier as of 2014, namely with four data records. If the country were completely removed from the analysis, the overall result (an R^2 value of 0.74) would be affected.

Moreover, it is debatable whether the regression model provides a significant contribution to explaining the dependent variable. In this case, the test statistic (F) and the critical F-value play a part. The latter ($4.2013E-17$) must be less than the test statistic (60.0055), and this is obviously the case. Thus, it can be concluded that the multiple regression model provides a statistically significant explanatory contribution.

Furthermore, the regression coefficients GE and public debt should be significant ($p\text{-value} < 0.05$). GE has a p-value of $6.0534E-18$. This is clearly less than 0.05. The GE coefficient is positive, which means that if the variable increases by one unit, the dependent variable (BTI) increases by 0.0445 units. The p-value of public debt comes to $1.6314E-05$ and, hence, it also is less than 0.05. The public debt coefficient of $-6.9107E-05$ is negative; therefore, it has a negative effect on the y-variable, which signals that an increase in public debt by one unit will cause the dependent variable to be reduced by $-6.9107E-05$. For this reason, the variable BTI can be derived with statistical verifiability through GE and public debt. Moreover, the varying p-values (GE and public debt) show that the quality of public administration is considered a decisive factor. A null hypothesis is considered unconfirmed, which is why it can be assumed that the statistical relationship between GE and debt affects the BTI (Status Index). Furthermore, the hypothesis is considered proven, even though Hungary is included in the analysis, which means that the hypothesis is confirmed with Hungary and even more so without this country. Accordingly, for all intents and purposes, the results can be considered robust.

However, in numerical terms, the strength of the effect that the quality of administration has on the transformation is relatively low because the value of 0.0445 indicates a weak positive effect. The model predicts a change in value of the dependent variable by 0.0445 if the value of the independent variable increases by one unit. However, this needs to be qualified by bearing in mind that the scale of values of the independent variable is broader than that of the dependent variable. The range of the dependent variable is from about 6.7 to 9.7, whereas values of about 41 to just short of 88 are possible for the independent variable. This means that when the value of the independent variable increases by ten points, the value of the dependent value is predicted to change by just under 0.5 points. In view of the different ranges of values, this does in fact describe a relatively appealing effect.

6 SUMMARY AND CRITICAL REFLECTION

The conclusion is preceded by a critical reflection on the design of the study.

Some questions remain unanswered although the quality of the regression model is positive given that R^2 has a value of 0.58 and, thus, supports the hypothesis. The open and unanswerable aspects can be attributed to the focused design of the study, i.e. questions that cannot be answered by the study indicate that other variables have an impact as well. As is frequently explained, a corresponding value of two variables x and y alone is not sufficient proof of an obligatory causal relationship. It goes without saying that there is room for alternative and

intervening factors that may influence the transformation. Complex processes cannot be completely reduced to individual parameters. They always are the result of the interaction between several actors and actor constellations as well as different structural and institutional conditions (see Lorig 2001, 207; Reiners 2008, 29–31). However, for example, it may be assumed that the partisan composition of the government concerned could be significant. Nonetheless, it isn't always of substantial importance because the pressure or the desire to gain access to the EU supersedes partisan politics in many cases, as has become evident in similar cases in the past (see e.g. Reiners 2013b, 76–79).

In addition, the quality of the result would be limited if only one independent variable were used. Therefore, another independent control variable is added. Even if the focus is on public administration and, correspondingly, on an influential and most likely the central actor in the overall government machinery, governments possibly need to be mentioned as additional potential factors of influence. However, they are included in some sense in the analysis through the interdependence between the public administration and the government within the government machinery of the political-administrative system. Furthermore, the wealth or economic strength of a country always is stated as a predictor (all in all Radosevic 2004, 641–666; Gabriel 2008, 190–193; Trüdinger 2008, 221–223; see Haensch and Holtmann 2008, 620–625). Hence, this economic factor is included in the analysis by way of the independent control variable.

The independent variable of quality of the public administration is based on the Government Effectiveness indicator, which comprehensively measures its quality, independence of political pressure and the quality of policy implementation. Accordingly, it integrates, per se, different factors and provides a detailed assessment of the public administration, which ensures a well-founded analysis and considerably relativizes any objections claiming that the set of independent variables is overly limited. Moreover, another control variable that was derived from the theoretical context is included and a multiple regression is calculated. A larger number of control variables, however, would be problematic because the GE index already includes very many factors and there is the risk of multicollinearity making the assessment unstable or inaccurate. All in all, it is evident that the quality of public administration is a decisive variable with relatively high explanatory power. In contrast, public debt barely has any impact on the transformation. In fact, as established in many cases elsewhere, the factor rather may prove conducive to stimulating transformation processes, acting as a catalyst or awakening willingness to intervene in existing structures and traditions and, hence, promoting a system's willingness to learn (see only Reiners 2016, 17–18).

Merging the GE and BTI indices in a correlation analysis is sometimes criticized because the WGI index is based on the BTI with respect to the GE dimension (Langbein and Knack 2010, 350–370; Kaufmann and Kraay 2023; see also Wagschal and Jäckle 2009; Brusis 2009). For this reason, it runs the risk of assessing a tautology. However, when referring to the BTI, the WGI primarily reverts to the Management Index, which is not included in the analysis of the dependent variable, and less to the Status Index that is included here. This considerably reduces the risk of a false tautological conclusion because of potential overlaps of the two indices. In addition, the BTI was adjusted for the two independent variables and possibly overlapping factors were subtracted out. It appears that there essentially weren't any other similar or identical indicators in the independent variables and dependent variable. In the end, possible objections can be mitigated because the correlation with the adjusted BTI does not manifest a substantially different result.

The regression model demonstrates the confirmation of the hypothesis. A well-functioning and efficient public administration promotes transformation. It has a significant positive impact on the transition to more democracy and a market economy. In statistical terms, this can be argued with a "double negative." What was not proven was that X doesn't influence Y or, to put it differently, a moderate indication shows that X affects Y. This effect supports the assumption that the public administration is a dominant actor in the process of implementing EU standards. Accordingly, this means that a functioning administration is a fundamental prerequisite to successfully achieve EU accession. It is recommended that future research be embedded in a larger longitudinal study and an expanded set of variables. To be sure, other factors have an influence on the process, too. Yet, the objective of the study was not to illuminate all effects, but rather to lay some groundwork. Even if the approach seems to limit somewhat the explanatory power, the study, based on its design, will be conducive to and fundamental for future research.

The topics of public administration and transformation offer ample starting points for research. Particularly against the background of globalization and new management concepts, public administrations, which are undergoing a transformation process in many countries, are interesting research subjects. Therefore, in view of the continuous modernization of states and against the background of European developments, policy analyses as well as qualitative and quantitative analyses that study, among other things, how administrations function and their effect, may be considered a focal point of research in political science and public administration

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POMEN KAKOVOSTI JAVNE UPRAVE ZA EVROPEIZACIJO

Javna uprava ima ključno vlogo v procesih tranzicije in modernizacije države. Njena kakovost pomembno vpliva na tranzicijske procese v vzhodnoevropskih državah, ki so se usmerile na pot priključevanja Evropski uniji. Ta hipoteza je potrjena z analizo nekdanjih socialističnih oziroma komunističnih držav, ki so postale članice Evropske unije v okviru dveh večjih širitvenih valov v letih 2004 in 2007. Te države so bile za uspešno vključitev v evropske integracije primorane izvesti obsežne notranje reforme, usmerjene v krepitev demokracije in vzpostavitev tržnega gospodarstva. Z uporabo kvantitativne raziskovalne zasnove je analizirano, ali dobro delujoča javna uprava pomembno prispeva k učinkovitosti in vzdržnosti tranzicijskih procesov. Rezultati kažejo, da kakovostna in učinkovita javna uprava pomembno spodbuja tranzicijo ter pozitivno vpliva na prehod v stabilnejšo demokracijo in delujoče tržno gospodarstvo.

Ključne besede: javna uprava; demokracija; tržno gospodarstvo; Evropska unija; evropeizacija.